

Russian scientists should be given the opportunity to abandon "Putin's affiliations"

Many universities across the world have severed scientific ties with Russian research institutions in response to Russia's full-scale military invasion of Ukraine (Gaid & Else, 2022). However, many of these universities have opened their doors to Russian scholars and students who do not support their government's military aggression by offering them visiting professor or graduate student positions.

Contrary to their policies towards Russian science, universities oblige researchers to retain their affiliation with Russian universities, which they indicate in their papers. Visiting researcher positions require applicants to have permanent positions at other universities. Similarly, graduate students have to continue to maintain relationships with Russian institutions, since they are unlikely to be able to complete their thesis during their visits, and have to return to Russia to defend their thesis.

This leads to a paradox - universities are trying to boycott "Putin's science", and at the same time they pay Russian scientists salaries, give them access to infrastructure, and then the achievements of these researches fall into the treasury of Russian universities, where it can be used by Putin's propaganda.

It is clear that university leaders are trying to provide support as soon as possible, and so they are using the opportunities of existing programs. However, in this emergency, it does not work well. New policies need to be introduced for such positions, in particular to allow scientists to work in Western universities without adhering to their Russian affiliations.

REFERENCE

Gaid, N., & Else, H. (2022). Global research community condemns Russian invasion of Ukraine. *Nature*, 603(7900), 209–210. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00601-w>

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